

Contributed Paper

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The capability of the radon method for deducing
a parameterisation of air-sea gas exchange

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As we show in an adjoining presentation [1], we are in a position to have available greatly improved radon measuring precision and rate of data acquisition, compared to what has been used in previous radon field work (e.g. [2]). However, our field data ([1], Fig. 1) indicate that there are still problems of converting the measured radon deficit in the oceanic mixed layer into a gas transfer velocity, w . Therefore, we discuss in the following the ultimate precision of the radon method.

The problem is that the ocean-atmosphere radon escape flux, F , is the net of all the other terms in the mixed-layer radon balance [1]. If time averaging is done to eliminate short term variations due to internal oceanic motions, we can write the balance as

$$(1) \quad \bar{F} = \lambda \cdot \bar{I} + \overline{\frac{\partial I}{\partial t}} - \frac{\bar{I}}{D} \overline{\frac{\partial D}{\partial t}} - \overline{\vec{u}_h \cdot \text{grad}_h I}$$

(a) (b) (c) (d)

(The last two terms are the advective term expanded, the last but one representing the local horizontal-current divergence; D = mixed-layer depth.*) The approximate uncertainties in \bar{F} , $\delta\bar{F}/\bar{F}$, contributed by terms (a) to (d) in equation (1) can be

* Only depth changes due to divergence of the horizontal mixed-layer flow are to be considered, i.e., thermocline entrainment has to be corrected for.

assessed as follows: Term (d) can be made small by making the observing ship drift with \vec{u}_h , and we therefore neglect the corresponding error for the time being. The other contributions to first order are

$$(a) \frac{\delta \bar{I}}{\bar{I}}, \quad (b) \frac{1}{\lambda \cdot \bar{I}} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{I}}{\partial t}, \quad (c) \frac{1}{\lambda \cdot \bar{D}} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{D}}{\partial t}$$

A typical value for (a) is $\lesssim 10\%$, the uncertainty being caused by systematic errors in I such as uncertainties of the radium-226 concentration. The values for (b) and (c) apparently depend on the precision to which time trends in I and D over the averaging period can be detected. If little variability in I and D is encountered, fractional changes larger than about 1% should be detectable (this corresponds to a detection limit for a mixed-layer depth change of ± 0.5 m if $D = 50$ m!). In this case, the values for (b) and (c) for a 12-h averaging period are about 11% each ($\lambda = 0.75/h$), so that the total uncertainty $\delta \bar{F}/\bar{F} \approx \pm 20\%$. During JASIN, variability in I and D was appreciable. The best detection limit that one could achieve under such circumstances we estimate at $\pm 2\%$, so that $\delta \bar{F}/\bar{F}$ rather would be about $\pm 30\%$.

In summary, for a 12 h averaging period one cannot expect to determine \bar{F} better than $\pm 20\dots 30\%$. For longer averaging periods the errors due to (b) and (c) decrease linearly, so that finally (a) becomes dominant, and $\pm 10\%$ presumably is an ultimate, ideal over-all error in the average radon escape flux, \bar{F} . Very little further uncertainty is introduced when converting \bar{F} to the gas transfer velocity \bar{w} , so that for the uncertainty of \bar{w} the same figures apply. The above considerations furthermore give a clear concept on how to carry out a gas exchange experiment in the field with the radon method. (On top of these, there are additional conditions, e.g., suitable mixed-layer depth and range of wind speeds, and homogeneous radium-226 concentration. A particular problem may be to find suitable high-wind conditions.)

We regard the mentioned problem with the JASIN data as being caused primarily by the large variability of the mixed-layer/

thermocline system. The ship was stationary, so that also term (d) comes in, which term may be appreciable particularly if an oceanic front crosses the position of the ship, for which there are indications during phase 2 of JASIN. We shall therefore look twice for variability when planning a future experiment. In such an experiment, we also shall take into account further parameters that may influence the gas transfer velocity, other than wind velocity which is the only parameter that has so far been considered in field work. We believe that the Trier meeting will give a sound basis for this part of the problem.

- [1] B. Kromer, W. Roether, Wind dependence of gas exchange determined in field experiments with the radon method.
- [2] Peng et al., JGR Vol. 84, C5.